

The Effect of Work-related Need Satisfaction and Gratitude on Happiness among Doctors

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to explore the effect of Work-related need satisfaction and Gratitude on Happiness among Doctors. This study is descriptive in nature and the correlation research design is used for the study. Respondents are required to answer a self-administered questionnaire consisting of socio-demographic questions. Work-related need satisfaction scale developed by Van den Broeck et al. (2010), The Gratitude Questionnaire-6 (GQ-6) (McCullough, Emmons & Tsang, 2002) and Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (Hills & Argyle, 2002). There will be a positive correlation among work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and wellbeing. 2) The level of work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and contentment will be high in Govt. doctors as compared to private doctors. 3) The level of work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and pleasure will be high among male doctors as compared to female doctors. 4) The level of work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and contentment will be low among non-local doctors as compared to local doctors. Findings infer that there was a positive and significant relationship between needs satisfaction, gratefulness and wellbeing. However significant correlation was found between work-related need satisfaction and gratefulness with wellbeing. 2) It is found that Need Satisfaction, gratefulness and wellbeing are all non-significant in Govt. doctors as compared to private doctors. 3) It was found that happiness were significantly different in different genders. However, there was non-significant difference among other variable of cross gender. 4) The results showed that there was a significant difference in need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness among local and non-local doctors.

Keywords: Need Satisfaction, Gratitude, Happiness

1. Introduction

In the present and competitive world, doctors live incredibly hard life. Due to their hard life conditions, they face challenges in life more than other persons. Some of these are difficult bosses, unsatisfying job condition financially unsatisfying circumstances, relationship problems because they have to spend more time in hospitals and they can be called for emergency at any time (Alexandros & Davidson, 2003).

Work-related need satisfaction is formed in connection with increased wellbeing and to less miserableness (Baard, Deci & Ryan, 2004). Individuals from different age groups and different societies may fulfill their psychological needs in different ways, everybody is thus likely to help from having the basic psychological needs (Latham & Pinder, 2005).

Psychological need satisfaction is the most important high value tools for individuals as water, mined substances, and good weather are most important for plants and flower (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Ali & Audi, 2016).

In self-determination theory, three basic psychological needs are need for freedom, need for accomplishment and need for connected. These are taken to be true to represent the important guiding tool that gives power to and gives direction to the person's behavior (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Sajid & Ali, 2018;).

First, the need for freedom represents individual's natural desire to use one's will and to experience a sense of good quality and psychological state of being free when doing an operation (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006).

Second, the need for accomplishment is defined as individuals' inherent desire to feel effective in interacting with the environment (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Senturk & Ali, 2021; Ali & Senturk, 2019)

Finally, the need for connected is defined as individuals' inherent inclination to feel connected to others, that is, to be a member of a group, to love and care and be loved and cared for (Baumeister & Leary, 1995).

In psychology, recent research has shown gratitude to have multiple positive effects, such as fostering prosocial behavior, maintaining intimate bonds and improving psychological and physical well-being. In fact, the popular press proclaims that being oriented around gratefulness is the remedy for limitless desires (McCullough, Kilpatrick, Emmons & Larson, 2001).

Well-being is of great importance to the most persons in general, and happiness has been discovered to be a highly valued and it's the purpose of the most people (Diener, 2000). Happiness, in the form of Joy, appears in every society as a basic to do with man's feelings. Feeling happy is deep to do with man's experience, and the most people are at least not strongly, softly, quietly happy much of the time (Diener & Diener, 1996).

1.1. Objectives of study

The aim of the present study are:

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- To explore the correlation among work-related need satisfaction and gratefulness on wellbeing.
- To study the level of work--related need satisfaction, gratitude and well-being among private and government doctors
- To study the work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and well-being across gender
- To find the level of work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and wellbeing among local and Non –Local doctors

1.2. Hypotheses

- There will be a significant positive correlation among work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and well-being.
- The level of work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness will be high in Govt. doctors as compared to private doctors
- The work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness will be high among Male doctors as compared to female doctors
- The level of work-related need satisfaction, gratefulness and well-being will be low among non-local doctor as compared to local doctors

2. Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature and the correlation research design is used for the study. The present study is an attempt to evaluate the effect of work-related need satisfaction and gratefulness on well-being among doctors of private and government hospitals of Multan division. The analysis is performed with SPSS version 22. They questionnaires of Work-related basic need satisfaction scale developed by Van den Broek et al. (2010), The Gratitude Questionnaire–6 (GQ-6) (McCullough, Emmons & Tsang, 2002) and Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (Hills & Argyle, 2002) are used in this study.

3. Results

In the present study the analyses are done on the sample of 200 Doctors (male and female) from the Govt. and Private Hospitals. Three parameters: Work-Related-basic need satisfaction, The Gratitude Questionnaire–6 (GQ-6) and Oxford Happiness Questionnaire are observed from each sampling unit. The detailed results are as follows:

Table: 1
Demographic Composition of sample of study
Total sample N=200

Demographics	N	Weighted %
Gender		
Male	100	50%
Female	100	50%
Local doctors	100	50%
Non Local doctors	100	50%
Government doctors	100	50%
Private doctors	100	50%

Table 1 shows the demographics composition of sample of the study. These demographics are Gender, Job status and Residential status

Table: 2
Mean, Standard Deviation and Pearson Correlation Coefficient of Study Variables (N = 200)

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1 Need Satisfaction	59.2	12.9	1		
2. Gratitude	28.9	6.8	0.453**	1	
3. Happiness	118.9	21.2	0.247**	0.335**	1

p**<0.01, p*<0.05

Mean, standard deviation and correlation coefficients of all variable included in the study. Above reveals that there is a positive and significant relationship between needs satisfaction, gratefulness and well-being.

Table: 3

Independent samples t-test for Equality of Means for Govt and Private Doctors									
	Mean		SD		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	T	df	Sig.
	Govt.	Private	Govt.	Private					
Need Satisfaction	60.12	58.18	12.19	13.59	1.94	1.82534	1.063	198	0.289
Gratitude	29.58	28.19	6.26	7.21	1.39	0.95461	1.456	198	0.147
Happiness	116.63	121.12	20.66	21.60	-4.49	2.98904	1.502	198	0.135

If the variables under study are all considered independent then t-test for equality of means can be applied as shown in above Table. All Govt. and Private doctors are compared and it is found that Need Satisfaction, gratefulness and well-being are all non-significant.

Table: 4

Independent samples t-test for Equality of Means across Gender (N=200)									
	Mean		SD		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	t	df	Sig.
	Female	Male	Female	Male					
Need Satisfaction	60.38	57.92	11.65	14.01	2.46	1.82217	1.35	198	0.179
Gratitude	28.11	29.66	7.14	6.32	-1.55	0.95337	1.626	198	0.106
Happiness	111.43	126.32	21.68	17.94	-14.89	2.81361	5.292	198	0.000

P<**0.01

According to the table all female and male doctors are compared across all categories of the data and it is found that well-being is significantly different in different genders. However there is non-significant difference among other variable of cross gender.

Table: 5

Independent samples t-test for Equality of Means for Local and Non-Local doctors (N=200)									
	Mean		SD		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	t	df	Sig.
	Local	Non-Local	Local	Non-Local					
Need Satisfaction	62.36	55.94	10.74	14.11	6.42	1.77276	3.62	198	0.00
Gratitude	31.15	26.62	5.91	6.84	4.53	0.9041	5.01	198	0.00
Happiness	121.99	115.76	20.18	21.83	6.23	2.97323	2.1	198	0.037

P<**0.01

According to the table all Local and Non-Local doctors are compared. There is significant difference in need satisfaction, gratefulness and well-being among local and non-local doctors.

4. Discussion

This research is an attempt to examine the impact of work-need satisfaction and gratitude on well-being. According to the first hypothesis that there will be a significant positive correlation among work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and well-being. The correlation was assessed with the help of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings infer that there was a positive and significant relationship between needs satisfaction, gratitude and well-being.

The second hypothesis is that the level of work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and well-being will be high in Govt. doctors. All Govt. and Private doctors were compared and it was found that Need Satisfaction, gratitude and happiness were all non-significant.

According to the third hypothesis, work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and well-being will be high among Male doctors. It was found that happiness is significantly different in different genders. However, there is non-significant difference among other variable of Need satisfaction and Gratitude across gender.

The fourth hypothesis states that the level of work-related need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness will be low among non-local doctor. It was inferred that there was a significant difference in need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness among local and non-local doctors.

5. Conclusion

The motivation behind this study was to discover the relationship of work-related need satisfaction and gratitude with happiness of doctors in Govt. and private sector. Results indicated that there was a positive and significant relationship need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness. It was also found that Need Satisfaction, gratitude and happiness were all non-significant in govt. and private doctors. It was found that happiness was significantly different in different genders. However, there was non-significant difference among other variable of Need Satisfaction and gratitude across gender. It was inferred that there was significant difference in need satisfaction, gratitude and happiness among local and non-local doctors.

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